

Practice for Micro-credentials

Problem encountered and objective

A **micro-credential** is a short, focused learning program that certifies mastery of a specific skill or competency. In short food supply chains (SFSCs), where high variability exists, there is a strong need for flexible learning, as each actor possesses different knowledge. Lifelong learning is increasingly difficult to actively pursue alongside work, as very little time is available for continuous skill development. Due to the lack of harmonized definitions and frameworks for micro-credentials within SFSC contexts and to facilitate advisory recognition and collaboration in the SFSCs it was necessary to create modular and flexible pathways that support lifelong learning and knowledge consistency via certificated learning materials.

Main results / outcomes

By creating micro-credentials to each freely accessible module, members of the SFSC systems can learn according to their knowledge, since smaller learning units allow users to acquire relevant expertise in smaller segments and relatively quickly, with each certificate guaranteeing validated competence. Furthermore, micro-credentials enable future full accreditation at the national level, as the process is not significantly different from that of complete curricula that would provide end-users with a unified framework that is easily interpretable across Europe, like the EQF system. This would improve applicability, foster greater acceptance, and facilitate smoother integration into the AKIS system as well as the accreditation of SFSC advisors in the long run. Furthermore, micro-credentials are easily enlargeable and updateable offering a good base for further learning materials.

Practical recommendations

The micro-credentials will be available for the developed 8 modules based on the targeted needs from SFSC advisors containing food production and technology, innovation, digitalization, marketing, labelling and crucial soft skills as well, offering a fast, tailored, reliable and time-flexible learning with no language barriers (since these topics can be easily translated to different languages, including the 24 official in EU) to help challenges such as seasonality, labour shortage or regulatory complexity in an easily understandable way including necessary skills from farmers to SFSC managers as well. The key topics were covered by considering the EIT Food Structure to ease accreditation processes.

Further information

Moodle link: (soon at EU4Advice platform <https://eu4advice.eu/>)

About this abstract

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EU4Advice is a project designed to create a network of SFSC advisors, policy-makers, researchers and farmers, working together towards the effective organizational set-up of the AKIS. It is intended to promote more sustainable and empowering SFSC models, which constitute a promising and emerging sustainable alternative to globalized food systems, with strong potential to empower both producers and consumers while, at the same time, reducing the environmental footprint and enhancing the competitiveness of the agri-food system.